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PROGRESSIVE PUNJAB- A PARADIGM SHIFT IN THE ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The Land of Five Rivers - Punjab is an Indian state known for its Vibrancy and Dynamism. Punjab is a perfect mix of traditional (agriculture) and modern (industry) growth. Punjab traditionally has been known as the “bread basket of India” because of its high levels of productivity and agricultural growth. Punjab is largely dependent on agriculture and the state has contributed to the central pool significantly towards strengthening India’s self-sufficiency. The state is well developed in terms of just not agriculture or industry but also in terms of upcoming infrastructure and rich educational opportunities-Punjab University, Punjabi University, Guru Nanak Dev University, Punjab Technical University and many more. Over the years, the state has been witnessing a change in all spheres be it education, infrastructure, upcoming thermal plants, migration to other countries, investment friendly environment, strong army base, border connections with Pakistan, tourist attractions etc. This paper shows its focus on how over a time of span, the economy of Punjab is undergoing changes thus impacting its economy.

Introduction

Economy of Punjab

The states major economic resources are its fertile land, the irrigation systems and its well-educated, technically sound population. These factors have contributed to achieve higher levels of productivity and a better competitiveness level in the global economy.

Agriculture

The economy of the state depends heavily on agriculture, industrial exports and tourism .The state is endowed with vast agricultural resources. Being an agricultural state the majority of its workers are engaged in farming and animal husbandry. The state produces most of India's grains than any other state in the country. Wheat, rice, sugarcane, cotton, fodder are the vital economic indicators of Punjab's agrarian society. The state has two crop seasons “Rabi”, the

spring harvest season and the “Kharif” the autumn harvest season. The rice produced in the state is marketed and processed in different types of rice mills. There are about 2,200 grain hullers mostly in rural areas of the state. The Punjab sugarcane industry has undergone a major overhaul during the last five decades. The sugar production too has increased in recent years. Morinda Co-operative sugar mill is one of the largest sugar crushing mills in the state with a daily crushing capacity of 4,000 tones. Animal husbandry has been an essential part of Punjab’s economic life. The dairy industry of the state is part of a long and proud agricultural tradition of the state. Punjab is one of the largest milk producing areas of India with a capacity of 10 per cent of the country’s total production capability. Moga, is one of the largest milk processing plants in the state with a total production capacity of 435 thousand liters of milk.

Some two-fifths of Punjab’s population is engaged in the agricultural sector, which accounts for a significant segment of the state’s gross product. Punjab produces an important portion of India’s food grain and contributes a major share of the wheat and rice stock held by the Central Pool (a national repository system of surplus food grain). Much of the state’s agricultural progress and productivity is attributable to the so-called Green Revolution, an international movement launched in the 1960s that introduced not only new agricultural technologies but also high-yielding varieties of wheat and rice.

Aside from wheat and rice, corn (maize), barley, and pearl millet are important cereal products of Punjab. Although the yield of pulses (legumes) has declined since the late 20th century, there has been a rapid increase in the commercial production of fruit, especially citrus, mangoes, and guavas. Other major crops include cotton, sugarcane, oilseeds, chickpeas, peanuts (groundnuts), and vegetables.

With almost the entire cultivated area receiving irrigation, Punjab is among India’s most widely irrigated states. Government-owned canals and wells are the main sources of irrigation; canals are most common in southern and southwestern Punjab, while wells are more typical of the north and the northeast. The Bhakra Dam project in neighbouring Himachal Pradesh provides much of Punjab’s supply of irrigation water. Major industries include the manufacturing of scientific instruments, agricultural goods, electrical goods, financial services, machine tools, textiles, sewing machines, sports goods, starch, tourism, fertilisers, bicycles, garments, and the processing of pine oil and sugar. Punjab also has the largest number of steel rolling mill plants in India, which are located in Steel Town Mandi Gobindgarh, District Fatehgarh Sahib.

Education

In Punjab, the state government manages 90.8 per cent of the recognized educational Institutions; nine per cent are non-government, aided and/or recognized institutions and only a negligible number comes under the control of the Centre. The number of non-governmental but recognized institutions is however higher in the case of high schools and senior secondary schools than primary and middle schools, i.e., one-fifth of the high schools and one-fourth of the senior secondary schools are non-governmental institutions. Punjab Government has made great strides in expanding access to education by opening new schools at all levels. The total number of schools increased from 8,891 in 1966-67 to 18,998 in 2001. The data reveal that the most massive expansion of schooling facilities took place during the 1970s-80s in Punjab, when the number of schools jumped from 9,394 to 16,050.

Although there has been a gradual increase in the number of institutions from the 1980s to 2000, the expansion has not been that significant as in the period 1970-80. The number of primary schools increased tremendously in the past. It rose to 7,256 in 1970 and reached 12,383 in 1980. At present it has already reached 13,076 (2000-01). The number of middle schools was 1,498 in 1980-81, increased to 2,545 in 1996-97, and is at present 2,534. High schools numbered 919 in 1969-70, 1,275 in 1974-75, 1,912 in 1980-81, 2,249 in 1990-91 and 2,199 in 2000-01. It is evident that the number of schools really increased only during 1970-80. Senior secondary schools too increased to 1,189 in 2000-01 from 520 in 1990.

The data of the survey conducted in 12,625 villages by the Education Department reveal that except for some remote/unserved areas, there is a primary school in almost every village. There is likelihood of shortage of primary schools in Mand/Kandi/Border and Bet areas of Punjab, because of their difficult terrain. However, at the other end, the data also show that there are only 39 per cent of villages, having elementary sections and only 21 per cent which have secondary sections.

Even if we consider the distance norm as laid down by government, there are only 84 per cent habitations which have a middle school within three kms. which means shortage of elementary sections in 16 per cent habitations. Similarly, there is also a shortage of secondary and senior secondary schools in 10 per cent and 20 per cent habitations, according to the distance norm of five kms. and eight kms. respectively).

The assessment of the number of schools reveals that though the state is progressing well and there has been a quantitative expansion of educational institutions in Punjab, the real increase in the number of schools has been just at the primary level. However, according to the present data, following the norm that there should be one secondary section for every 1.8 elementary section, the shortage comes to nearly 6,000 secondary schools. This indicates that even if all the secondary schools are upgraded upto the senior secondary level, there will still be a shortage of nearly 3,000 schools.

Alternate Schooling

Non- formal education for children in the 6-14 age -group: In pursuance of the National Policy on Education, 1986, the Central Government provides help for the establishment of non-formal education centres. But in Punjab, neither the government, nor NGOs, nor voluntary agencies run any such centres. Non-formal education was carried on until 1991, but there are no data available. However, since 1991, Punjab has no facility for non-formal education at the primary or upper primary level for children in the age group 6-14. In only one district of Amritsar, a Chandigarh- based NGO applied to the Centre for starting NFE centres in 90 slums of the district. This project has been approved. But at present, no non-formal educational centre is operational. It is, however, proposed that under the Sarv Shiksha Abhiyan, in the Tenth Plan, the Education Guarantee Scheme and alternative innovative education will be initiated.

Open school programme for children in the 14-18 age -group: The National Policy 1986, had proposed alternative education/open schools at the secondary level to provide access to dropouts, working children and girls. However, the state's effort so far has been to bring the children to mainstream/ formal schooling, and hence not much work has been done on open schools, though the large number of school dropouts warrant such an initiative.

Punjab started the open school programme in 1992, as an integral part of Punjab School Education Board as a centre of open learning to cover the gap at the secondary level. PSEB is operating the programme with 175 centres and 16,000 students. It has not developed any separate set of operational procedures except providing flexibility in the number of chances for passing examinations. In 1994-95 the open school was converted into a correspondence

course, as a distance education programme. It has the same curriculum, examination and certification process as in formal schools. Except for this programme at the matriculation level, there is no alternative schooling in the state at present for the out-of-school children in the 14-8 age group. The open school in Punjab is dependent only on student fees. In the absence of any financial support and requisite publicity, it has not realized its full potential. Recently, the state government claims to have formed VEDCs in the villages to check drop-out rates under SSA.

However, there are a few concerns on which there must be a strong focus which would be directly or indirectly affecting the Economy of Punjab:

1. Optimal upgradation of primary schools to elementary level and secondary

schools to senior secondary level: The state has nearly achieved universal access to primary schools, except in certain Mand/Border/Kandi and Bet areas. Special strategies like the Education Guarantee Scheme (EGS) should be envisaged for these remote areas without accessibility to basic primary education. The focus should be now on achieving universalized accessibility at the elementary level and easy accessibility at the secondary level, by optimally merging the number of schools under two categories instead of four, i.e., one at the elementary level and the other at the secondary level.

2. Rationalization and redistribution of staff: At present, a major chunk of the expenditure on education is on salaries/state liabilities, leaving very little for actual development in education. The state government should try to utilize optimally the expenditure. Staffing in Punjab needs to be redistributed, restructured and rationalized. It is very important to upgrade the primary schools to middle level, so that the shortage of teachers at the former is compensated by the excess at the latter, the teacher-pupil ratio being lower at the middle level than at the primary level.

3. Focus on pre-service/in-service teachers' training: The government should enhance the competency and skills of the teachers by promoting pre-service and in-service training for them. DIETS (District Institution of Education and Training at elementary level)/GISTC's (Government In-service and Training Centres at secondary level) and other training institutions must be optimally utilized for this purpose. Such pre-service and in-service training programmes should be constantly reviewed and strengthened, as its quality has a direct bearing on the quality of education in the state.

4. **Focus on teacher empowerment:** The critical role of teachers in the entire education set-up must be realized. Emphasis should be made to address their professional development needs. Processes should be set up to initiate a participative mode for the teachers in the development of curriculum, text-book, teaching-learning material and methodologies. However, simultaneously the teachers have to be made more responsible and performance-oriented.

5. **Revamping the curriculum:** There should be a special thrust to make education at elementary level useful and relevant for children. At present, it is highly regimented with uniform courses. The state has been blindly following the national curriculum without considering the special conditions at the grass root level of Punjab. Hence modernization of the syllabus with more flexibility in the choice of subjects is recommended. Curriculum framework should be based on compulsory and flexible subjects, wherein the children have the choice to opt for the subject of their interest.

6. **Changing the mindset of parents:** As far as the social and cultural handicaps of enrollment and retention of girls in schools is concerned, the NGOs and PRIs need to be associated effectively to initiate an attitudinal change in the parents of the girl child.

7. **Enhance incentives to all children in government schools:** The various incentives being provided by the government should be for all children, irrespective of caste criteria (as being adopted today) to achieve the goal of universalization of education.

8. **English should be started in class 6:** According to the new Education Policy of the state, the English language has to be started in class 3 in government schools. But it is strongly felt that it is difficult for the child to bear the burden of an additional language at such a tender age. His understanding capacity is limited in the formative years and, therefore, it is strongly recommended that English should be started in class 6 and not in class 3. The English language cannot be avoided, but emphasizes needs to be given to the mother tongue.

Industry

Punjab is one of the most industrialized states in India. The state has a large manufacturing sector serving both the local and exports sectors. The large and small scale factories are scattered in all parts of the state.

The state has essentially an agrarian economy with a lower industrial output as compared to other states of India. A prominent feature of the industrial scenario of the Punjab is its small sized industrial units. There are nearly 194,000 small scale industrial units in the state in addition to 586 large and medium units. Ludhiana is an important centre for industry. In the 1980s there was a chance of a Hero Honda and Maruti Suzuki plant to be set up in Ludhiana but due to some circumstances of terrorism it was cancelled.

Important industries

The industrial units in the state are broadly divided into three-

- Agro-based industrial units
- Machinery units
- Chemical units

Textile industry

The state produces nearly 70% of the best quality cotton in India. In spite of several advantages, there is one major disadvantage that the total spindlage capacity of the state is only 1.5% of the country. Ludhiana is known as Manchester of India.

The cotton mills are located at Abohar, Malout, Phagwara, Amritsar, Kharar, Mohali and Ludhiana. Malerkotla, Abohar, Malout and Bhatinda are important for cotton ginning and pressing and nearly 25.3 mln (25,300,000) bales of cotton are pressed annually over here. About 97 million kilograms of yarn and 36.5 million metres of cloth were produced in the cotton textile mills of Punjab.

Overall textile production of Punjab is predictable at Rs.105000 Million, as well as Rs.32500 Million sell abroad of knitwear, shawls, made-ups (bed sheets, pillow cases, duvet covers, and curtains) and yarns. The direct and indirect employ of textile doings in the state of Punjab is predictable at 2 Million people. “Said Mr H.S.Cheema, Chairman, Punjab committee, Northern India Textile Mills Association (NITMA)”State of Punjab produces just about 1.8 to 2.2 million bales, about 11-12% of the country's production of cotton. But only 43% of the

cotton yarns formed in Punjab is used within the states and remaining is sold outside the state.

Sugar industry

The sugar mills in Punjab are located at Batala, Gurdaspur, Bhogpur, Phagwara, Nawanshahr, Zira, Morinda, Rakhra, Dhuri, Fazilka, Nakodar, Dasua, Budhewal, Budhladha, Mukerian, Tarn Taran, Ajnala, Faridkot, Jagraon, Amloh, Patran and Lauhka. Butter Sivan Near Baba Bakala One of the salient feature of the sugar industry is that out of the 22 mills, 15 are in the Co-operative sector and 7 are privately owned. Compared to the state of Uttar Pradesh and some other Indian states, the size of the sugar mills in Punjab is small. The Co-operative sugar mill at Morinda is the biggest in the state with a daily crushing capacity of 4,000 tonnes of sugarcane. Six of the cooperative sugar mills are inoperative while the remaining nine crush cane during the season which is about 150 days.

Dairy industry

The primary source of milk and other dairy products in the state is the buffalo. The state ranks at the top in the country in the availability of milk after Haryana and Gujarat.

The milk plants are mainly located at Verka (Amritsar district), Ludhiana, Mohali, Jalandhar, Patiala, Hoshiarpur, Gurdaspur, Ferozepur, Sangrur, Bhatinda, Faridkot, Nabha, Moga, Kot Kapura and Hamira. The plant at Moga is the biggest plant in the state with a processing capacity of nearly 435 thousand litres of milk.

Power

Total energy of the state is provided by the PSPCL own Thermal Plants a) 1260MW GURU GOBIND SINGH SUPER THERMAL PLANT at Ropar, b) 440MW Guru Nanak Dev Thermal Plant at Bhatinda, c) 920MW Guru Hargobind Thermal Plant at Lehra Mohabbat and its own Hydro Power Plants i) 110MW Shanan Power house at Joginder Nagar, ii) 600MW Ranjit Sagar DAM at Shah Pur Kandi, iii) 91.35MW UBDC power houses, iv) 207MW Mukerian Hydel Project, v) 134MW Anand Pur Sahib Hydel Channel, vi) Mini and Micro Hydro Power Plants on Sirhind Canal and its distributerries. IN addition to that it gets its share from Yhydro Power Plants under the control of BBMB. a) 1325MW Bhakra Dam Left and Right Bank Power Houses b) 155MW Hydro Power Plants on Bhakra Main Line at

Ganguwal and Kotla, c) 396MW Hydro Power Plant at Pong, d)990MW Power Plant at Dehar. A new Thermal plant is set up in Rajpura(Punjab) with 1400 megawatt of power capacity inaugurated on 8th Dec 2013. Another Thermal Plant in Bathinda with capacity of 1980 Megawatt power will come up soon.

The common pool projects are the Bhakra Nangal Complex, the Dehar Power Plant and the Pong Power Plant. Punjab shares about 51% of the Power generated from the Bhakra Nangal Complex. 48% from the Power generated at the Pong Project.^[7]

Common pool projects

- Bhakra Nangal Complex
- The Upper Bari Doab Canal System (UBDC)
- The Shanah Power House

Thermal electricity

- Guru Nanak Dev Thermal Plant, Bathinda was completed in 1974. The Guru Nanak Thermal plant has four units of 110X4 MW capacity.
- Ropar thermal power plant consists of six units capable of generating 210 MW each. The plant is spread over an area of about 2,500 acres (10 km²) on the banks of River Sutlej.
- A 1980 MW thermal plant is under execution at Talwandi Sabo in Bathinda District by Sterlite industries.
- A 540 MW thermal plant is under implementation at Goindwal Sahib in District Amritsar by GVK Power.
- A 2640 MW thermal plant at Gidderbaha (District Bhatinda) and a 2100 MW Thermal Plant at Rajpura are in the pipeline.
- A number of bio-mass and AGro-Waste based power plants are under construction by Private Companies in collaboration with PEDDA based on renewable energy.

The majority of the industrial workers are engaged in small scale industries that make up 160,000 units (Estimates 2010). Large and medium business units are four hundred in number (Estimates 2010). The state's diverse industries range from Steel Rolling, scientific instruments, agricultural goods, electrical goods, bicycles, garments, machine tools, textiles,

sewing machines to manufacturing of sports goods. Over the past few years the industrial sector employed over a million. The state has positioned itself as a key destination for operations of multinational companies in a variety of industries. In recent years, the state has successfully attracted many big-names and reputed global companies such as Nippon, Hitachi, Fujitsu, Nestle, Glaxo, Smithkline and Motorola. The state economy has witnessed rapid growth in the bicycles manufacturing industry. Today the state of Punjab is the largest bicycles manufacturer in India. Handicrafts and cottage industries of the state have been extremely popular. Punjab has more than 39,000 (Estimates 2010) small cottage industries providing widest avenues for the state's labours.

Punjab in next 5 years

Development of strong inter-relationships and interdependence of Punjab with the neighbouring states of Haryana, Himachal Pradesh and Jammu and Kashmir will ensure sustainability and conservation of natural resources of all the states, viz., land, water and bio-diversity. Scientific afforestation, forest management and efficient use of water resources of the neighbouring hill states will benefit not only these states but also Punjab and other states in terms of additional hydro-power, reduced floods, drought and soil erosion, recharge of depleting underground water table and stabilization of the climate. Strong inter-state linkages will ensure effective conservation of natural resources and mutual and long-term benefit for the people of the region. As a consequence, the nation has a whole would proper. Looking towards 2020 one sees the landscape of Punjab dotted with high yielding, remunerative, market-oriented crops, supported by technologies that ensure efficient use of inputs, land and water resources for optimum production per unit area. Modern cultivation procedures will be in position with the use of aqua-culture, poly-houses, drip and sprinkler irrigation, bio-fertilizers and bio-pesticides, vermiculture, bio-technology, etc., which are cost effective and help increase quality production. The corporate sector will be involved in farm services, marketing, establishing of processing and value addition units and developing direct forward-backward linkages between the cultivators and the factory. Strong pro-active agri-research and extension programmes will be attuned to present and future requirements, coupled with government policies in favour of farmers, farming and agro-industry.

Based on experiences and concerns perceived from primary as well as secondary information, the vision for rural development must be viewed as an integral part of the development process. It will be reflected in a positive change in rural areas, both in a quantitative and a

qualitative sense. There will be diversified agriculture with value addition, cent per cent literacy, universal access to health services, higher skills for employment for all, the widest dissemination of knowledge through Information Technology, closer rural-urban standards in social, economic, human and physical infrastructure, a rural society sensitive to gender equality, cent per cent coverage and access to safe drinking water, easy access to micro-finances for underprivileged sections of the society, transfer of funds, functions and functionaries to PRIs, empowerment of Panchayati Raj Institutions for good governance, and the environment will be protected.

In the sphere of the development of industries, Punjab will focus on value-added agro-food processing, light engineering, hosiery and knowledge-based industries, such as biotechnology, pharmaceutical and electronics, attain a position of leadership and excellence in producing quality products and emerge as a major exporter by 2020, The SSI sector will be helped to bridge the technological and management gaps with the advanced world. It will acquire the culture of continuing innovation, upgradation and modernization and achieve a competitive edge in the global market and thus accelerate growth and promote employment and exports. An industrial Infrastructure of international standards will be created by setting up industrial clusters, parks and zones with the state-of-the-art technology. Government will only be an effective facilitator and enabler in all these activities.

Punjab's future is urban. By 2020, Punjab will have about 45 per cent urban population or even more. Well managed 'urbanization' will facilitate and sustain economic growth, improve service delivery and develop environmental infrastructure to improve quality of life. The 'urban development strategy' will promote good governance, provide 100% coverage of basic civic services and adequate housing to the shelter less urban poor, reduce urban poverty and ensure efficient management of municipal assets and development of municipal lands for income generation.

Poverty will be substantially reduced to make cities productive. ULBs will create poverty alleviation funds to provide employment, security and opportunity - goals envisaged in the *World Development Report 2000-01* - to create 'cities without slums' and protect urban environment in the long run. The people will be active participants in municipal affairs and thus ensure the sustainability of cities. They will be involved in the preparation of the development plans to meet the challenges and the growing needs of urban population.

Drug Abuse in Punjab

The problem of drug addiction in Punjab is, in many ways, unique and therefore needs to be understood with reference to its social and economic context. In most countries, “drug use is linked to urbanization” as well as poverty. The situation in Punjab paints a very different picture. Firstly, the problem is occurring on a scale of exceptional proportion. According to a 2011 report on drug abuse and alcoholism in Punjab by the Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports, “40 per cent of Punjabi youth in the age group of 15 to 25 years have fallen prey to drugs”.

If we were to apply this statistic to the total youth population of Punjab, this would suggest a population of roughly 1.5 to 2 million young Punjabis addicted to drugs. The long-term effects this would have on the demography of the state could be potentially devastating, especially since many within this population of drug addicts are soon to enter their productive and re-productive years. Such a sizeable population of drug users could lead to, in the future, increasing levels of crime, broken marriages, destroyed families and children who face psychological, emotional and developmental problems as a result of drug-addict parents. Secondly, the demographic of users (most of whom are middle- and upper-middle class rural youth) varies vastly from the global stereotype of the drug-addict as a poverty-stricken urbanite. Therefore, an analysis of Punjab-specific social and economic factors may help explain why and how so many of Punjab’s youth have gone down the path of drug addiction.

Conclusion:

According to India Today, a leading magazine in India, Punjab was recognised as the best overall state since 2003 and has been able to retain the top position every year. It affords the best quality of life to its residents. According to the India State Hunger Index, Punjab has the lowest level of hunger in India. The Agriculture production in the state has reached a plateau. The soil health in the state has been deteriorating with the continuation of rice-wheat rotation by farmers due to assured profits as compared to other crops. The higher yield realization per unit area is also responsible for reduction of nutrients in the soil. In nutshell, domination of wheat-paddy in food grains, stagnating productivity, in the absence of breakthrough in new high yielding varieties, strains on marketing infrastructure, dwindling ground water resources and decline in profitability etc. are problems which requires attention. There is **High Incidence of Debt on Farmers**. To capitalize on the 'Progressive Punjab' brand, Mohali received its share of major upliftment for the two-day Progressive Punjab Investors' summit.

Punjab's maiden investor summit has already raised few eyebrows with the overnight construction of roads, streetlights and railings. As one entered the complex, the freshly carpeted roads had reflectors on either side. Standing outside the venue, a local resident claimed, "For us, this has been a blessing in disguise. Last-minute beautification of Mohali, and roads right in front of our house is a pleasant sight. Seven days ago, it was a different scene altogether. We had roads full of hawkers selling cigarettes. But, now because of the high-profiled event, they were asked to move."

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